

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Krokeyi, Wisdom Selekekeme, Eniekezimene, Francis Ariayefa, and Ekainsai, Stephen Zion. (2020), Impact of Higher Education Students Loan Scheme on Manpower Development in Bayelsa State. In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.3, No.3, 637-651.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.03.03.197

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Impact of Higher Education Students Loan Scheme on Manpower Development in Bayelsa State

Wisdom Selekekeme Krokeyi¹, Francis Ariayefa Eniekezimene², Stephen Zion Ekainsai³

¹Department of Economics, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.
Email: selekekeme2000@gmail.com: +2348036777252

²Department of Economics, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State
Email: zimex2007@yahoo.com: +2348030851792

³Department of Economics, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State
Email: zionekainsai@gmail.com: +2348078205149

Correspondence: Wisdom Selekekeme Krokeyi. Email: selekekeme2000@gmail.com: +2348036777252

Abstract

The study investigated the impact of Higher Education Students Loan Scheme on Manpower Development in Bayelsa State. The research work was anchored by the human capital model. The study adopted Raosoft calculator to determine the size of the sample from the population of study and a sample size of 377 respondents was arrived at using the calculator and were distributed amongst students of Bayelsa state origin in higher institutions of learning and retrieved 100 copies. This shortfall in the total number of retrieved questionnaire was a result of the lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The distribution of sponsorship across students of Bayelsa state origin reveal that 63% percent were sponsored by Parent/Guardians, 3% percent were by Bayelsa Higher Education Students Loan Scheme, 2% percent are on scholarship while 33% percent are self-sponsored. The data obtained from the survey were analyzed with SPSS. The paper recommends that the Board should expand its scope beyond payment of school fees. Secondly, the Board should relax its policy on provision of guarantors to access loans and concentrate on withholding certificates as collateral.

Keywords: Bayelsa, BHESLS, Education, Human Capital Model, Raosoft

1. Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

The development of manpower development in Bayelsa State is important and critical which has spur the governments over the years to explore other avenues to improve on human capital development. Bayelsa state was created in 1996 from the old River State. Since its creation, the government saw the need to improve on the human capital development, which it saw as investment, though education creates costs in the present but delivers benefits in the future. While students are in school, expenses they incur include both direct costs (tuition, books) and opportunity costs. Future benefits include increased earnings, improved health and longer life. To pay the current costs of their education, students need liquidity. In a business deal, a borrower would put up collateral in order to

fund a potentially profitable investment. The collateral would typically include any capital goods used in the fledging enterprise such as a building or machinery.

In Bayelsa State, the significance of education and manpower development for the growth and development is critical to successive governments as exhibited in governments' policies and programmes, particularly in the educational sector. As a matter of fact, in Bayelsa State, the government alone cannot continue to shoulder the burden of funding education. Consequently, the Bayelsa State Higher Education Students' Loan Board was created by the Restoration Government of Hon. Henry Seriake Dickson to provide unfettered access to loans for tertiary education in the state. The Board was established to offer financial assistance to financially challenged students of Bayelsa State origin enrolled in various higher institutions nationwide. The Board has several functions: to supervise, coordinate, administer and monitor the management of the Students' Loan Scheme in the State; develop requirements, guidelines, criteria and modalities for qualification, disbursement and repayment of loans; control, monitor and coordinate the students loan account/fund and ensure compliance in respect of disbursement and repayment; monitor and maintain information on academic records, year of graduation, national service and employment in order to ensure that they commence repayment of the loan as and when due; liaise with the employer of the guarantors and conclude documentation with employers to ensure that the required sum to be deducted from the guarantors salary and remitted to the student loan fund/account as directed by the board; exercise all legal rights towards recovering all loans and enforce the provisions of the law; issue a report to the House of Assembly and the Governor on the performance of the students loan on quarterly basis; notwithstanding any provisions of the law or any other legislation applicable in the state, provide rules and guidelines, including methods of application, qualification, criteria and proof of identification to prevent multiple allocation to an individual impersonator to non-existing person and similar vices; enter into any negotiation, agreement, contractual relationship, such as may be necessary or expedient for the discharge of the functions of the Board; and to conduct studies, researches, and investigations that may further the attainment of the goal and development of the Students' Loan Scheme in the state.

The Board has as objectives among others to: increase equitable access to technical and higher education in the state, facilitate the mobilization of funds to provide interest free revolving loans to state indigenes studying in institutions of higher learning in the country for the payment of tuition fees and other related expenses, ensure constant and sustainable supply of loans to qualified students' applicants for the purpose of providing qualitative education, provide opportunities for qualified students of Bayelsa State origin who may not be able to afford higher education on their own, ensure a balance in discipline and competence diversity in higher education in the state, develop and support course critical to the development of the state and to ensure quality education to indigenous students through quality assurance and supervision, and to create a pool and guaranteed supply of competent manpower in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

The Bayelsa State government established the Higher Education Students' Loan Board to provide loans to assuage the financial predicaments of indigent students of the State. In keeping with its responsibilities, the Board has provided loans to institutions of higher learning in the state and still providing such loans to students of the state who are eligible to benefit from the scheme. Preliminary findings suggests that about 568 students of the state-owned Niger Delta University; 100 students from the Federal University Otuoke; 378 from the African University, Toru-orua; 174 from Bayelsa State Medical University; and none from the state-owned College of Education at Sagbama have benefited from the scheme. However, has the Board been able to provide a pool and guaranteed supply of competent manpower in Bayelsa State? Answer to this question is critical to measure the impact of the higher education students' loan scheme on manpower development in Bayelsa State. This is the motivation of the study.

Many studies conducted on the Higher Education Students Loans Scheme (HESLS) have mostly concentrated on its success, sustainability and effectiveness on loans issuance and repayment. No such study has been conducted on the impact of higher education students' loan on manpower development in Bayelsa State.

The study, therefore, seeks to examine the impact of Higher Education Students Loan Scheme on manpower development in Bayelsa State with specific objective of to examine the impact of Higher Education Student Loan Scheme (HESLS) on students' access and completion of education.

Theoretical Framework

This study is established on the human capital theory.

Human Capital Model

The human capital theory (Becker, 1962) posits that education is an investment that generates higher expected returns to the individual over his/her lifetime. Hence, student loans are considered investment loans rather than consumption ones where consumers maximize expected utility by the tenets of neoclassical economic theory (see e.g., Schwartz and Finnie, 2002; Oreopoulos and Petronijevic, 2013; Avery and Turner, 2012). Becker (1962) assumes that in deciding to invest in human capital by attending college, a person would conduct a cost-benefits analysis of the investment and follow the investment decision criterion dictated by the standard economic theory of investment – that is invest if the discounted benefits exceed the discounted costs. The benefits are the expected future higher earnings accruing after completing higher education. The costs include the opportunity cost of higher education (earnings foregone while in college) and other direct education costs such tuition fees, transportation, etc. (Becker, 1962; Li, 2013; Avery and Turner, 2012). However, it is widely recognized that determining these costs and benefits and thus making an optimal investment decision is complex due to several factors, including incomplete information which may lead to underestimation or overestimation of costs and benefits, uncertainty about future economic and social conditions which may affect success in college, the cost of college and earning prospects, and behavioral idiosyncrasies such as degree of risk aversion which may affect optimal investment decisions (Oreopoulos and Petronijevic, 2013; Li, 2013).

Financing is part of the decisions to obtain a higher education qualification. All things being equal, people will tend to follow the Pecking Order Model (Myers and Majluf, 1984) that ranks internal financing first in the hierarchy of financing sources. Thus, students would prefer to finance their education, using personal and family sources of income first and would consider taking loans if they face financial constraints. Loan take up and the amount borrowed are influenced by supply and demand factors whose effects are usually difficult to completely delineate (Li, 2013). On the demand side, standard economic theory suggests that students who are not averse to risk, averse to debt and have high discount rates would be more inclined to take up student loans; they will also accumulate high loan debt (Oosterbeek and van den Broek, 2009).

Besides, there are a number of critics towards this theory. The opponents of this theory argue that “education acts as a screening device, since it calls for a certificate, a Bachelor’s degree or any of its kind which allows a person to get well-paid jobs without direct upsetting their efficiency”. Thus, awareness of high level of return on the individual’s higher level of education has been one of the bases for the introduction of cost-sharing with students in various universities of higher education. Likewise, HCT plays a vital role in evolving the connection between education and economic development of the country.

With this theory on hand, this paper examines the impact of the Higher Education Loan system with regard to students from low-income background based on its fairness and access. Therefore, application of this theory expects the policy makers and actors in Bayelsa to reflect and effectively implement their cost-sharing policy through higher education loan for the better allocation to the needy students, particularly those from poor and low-income backgrounds.

Empirical Literature

Several studies have been carried out to evaluate the nexus between higher education loan and access, impact as well as perception of higher education in both the developed and developing countries. Some of the empirical findings of these studies are presented in this study.

Canton and Blom (2004) studied the impact of student loans on access to higher education and performance, the case of student loan programme (SOFES) in Mexico. They hypothesized that financial aid to students in tertiary education can contribute to human capital accumulation through two channels: increased enrollment and improved student performance. With regard to the first channel, enrollment, results from the Mexican household survey indicate that financial support has a strong positive effect on university enrollment. Given completion of upper secondary education, the probability of entering higher education rises by 24 percent. Two data sources were used to investigate the second channel, student performance. Administrative data provided by SOFES were analyzed, using a regression-discontinuity design, and survey data which enabled a similar analysis, using a different control group. Empirical results suggested that SOFES recipients showed better academic performance than students without a credit from SOFES. However, the results cannot be interpreted as a purely causal impact of the student loan programme, since the impacts also could reflect (self-) selection of students.

Arora and Kaur (2016) investigated the status of higher education and education loan in India with special reference to Punjab. India's higher education system is the third largest in the world and has rapidly grown over the years. But unfortunately, there are several issues and challenges like access, equity, efficiency and excellence in higher education which has to be tackled efficiently. Out of these, access can be achieved only if higher education is affordable to all. Data shows that higher education institutions and enrolments are increasing with time and in line with this, percentage of education loan is also growing.

Dewan, Goel and Malhotra (2013) carried out a study in the Palwal and Faridabad District of Haryana, India, regarding the student perception about education loan and to compare male and female students with respect to various loan features like value addition, mortgage, effectiveness, eligibility criteria, procedure or convenience, disbursement and rate of interest regarding education loan. The education loan is to provide financial support to deserving students for pursuing education loan in India and abroad. The research was conducted on undergraduates and graduate students. Data has been collected through personal survey. Descriptive statistical tool like mean, standard deviation, co-variance and t-test were used for data analysis. The results revealed a number of issues including high rate of interest which retarded student participation, mortgage was not flexible, and eligibility criterion was not based on merit, distorted loan disbursement procedure and thus low value addition. The study thus recommended that the Authorities should address these problems to improve value addition in the student loan scheme and enhance access to higher education in the District.

Patra, Ray and Chaudhuri (2017) presents evidence of a strong positive impact of education loan availability on tertiary education outcomes in India. They evaluated the performance of a model education loan scheme introduced by the Indian Central Bank in 2001 that has drastically increased the availability of education loans in India. First, they estimated the impact of the increased availability of education loans on the years of schooling attained by an individual by exploiting the variation in the number of education loan accounts across districts and the exposure to the programme across age cohorts. They found that one standard deviation increase in the number of education loan accounts leads to a 6.17% improvement in years of schooling over the sample mean. Then they estimated the effect of availability of education loans on an individual's decision to enroll for higher education, by making use of across district and over time variation in the number of education loan accounts. The results suggested that one standard deviation increase in the number of education loan accounts results in a 6.87% increase in higher education enrolment over the sample mean. The study also found heterogeneous effects of education loans on enrolment and years of schooling, with the effects being more pronounced for the relatively disadvantaged groups across gender, caste and location (rural/urban).

Sadiq (2015) sought to ascertain whether the student loan trust fund (SLTF) has helped improve access to tertiary education in Ghana, using Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST) as a case study. Using a systematic random sampling method, 285 students already on the SLTF were sampled and questionnaires were administered to them. Using descriptive statistics to analyze the data, the study revealed that the SLTF has improved access to tertiary education in Ghana. The study further revealed the SLTF is managed well to meet its purpose of enhancing accessibility. However, the amount paid as loan per academic year to students was not enough to meet all the needs of the students. Despite methodological and generality limitations, the study provided

important findings relevant to improving the SLTF in Ghana. As such, the study recommended that the loan amount be increased and loans paid on time to help students on the scheme.

Nyoni (2018) studied the impact of higher education loan system among students from low-income background in Tanzania. The study used the document analysis technique. The Authors used relevant literature, officially published statistical data and various theoretical justifications for examining the impact of higher education loan towards students from low-income background. The results of this study identified some challenges leading to a misallocation of fund to the needy students, application of Means Testing being one of them. Meanwhile, the study recommended careful planning and effective use of means testing with a sustainable operational mechanism which should address the issue of parity and justice for the needy students in accessing higher education in Tanzania.

Kyaligonza (2017) examined the performance of the student loan scheme in Uganda. Making reference to related literature, views of selected stakeholders, and the performance of government's earlier lending programmes, the study identifies gaps in the performance of the scheme. These were in the areas of application procedures; disbursement; and structures for recovery. To enhance the reach of the loan scheme, the study recommended that government decentralizes some of its operations to district levels. Furthermore, it was recommended that the loan application forms be stationed at Advanced Level Secondary Schools to ease access. Also, the Higher Education Students Financing Board (HESFB) should sensitize the general public about the law governing the university education loan scheme.

Onen, Ajuaba, Oceng and Ndaruhutse (2015) examined the management of students' loan schemes in three African countries (Ghana, Kenya and South Africa). It was intended for the discernment of best practices and weaknesses of such schemes in order to draw lessons for younger loan schemes like the one and a half-year-old loan scheme of Uganda. The study was triggered by recurring challenges younger loan schemes experience despite available lessons to draw from older ones. Literature search and desk study were used to collect data. Study results revealed that besides the usual legal challenge that virtually every younger loan scheme appears to face, there are several problems loan schemes in Africa face including the difficulties to: create credible loan boards, identify the right loan beneficiaries, determine appropriate loan amounts, create reliable data-bases, and institute an effective and efficient loan disbursement and recovery systems. The study concluded that the problems faced by younger loan schemes in Africa are embedded within the political, social and economic systems and unless these structural difficulties are addressed, younger loan schemes are poised for grueling challenges.

3. Methodology

Every study is guided by research questions which requires to be treated/answered. The systematic ways of designing how such research question are tackled, the researchers plan about it is research methodology. This is the plan of the work; the techniques required in the research etc. The appropriate data has to be collected using the most efficient method which relies on the study method. This requires a system of models, procedures and techniques used to find the results of a research problem (Panneerselvam, 2011).

The study adopted a closed-ended survey questionnaires to collect primary data which will help in analyzing the data qualitatively for a holistic and narrative understanding of the challenges associated with the students' loan in Bayelsa state.

A pilot study was done to ascertain the designed questionnaire was appropriate and basically, to know its weaknesses in collection of suitable data such that it can be improved on with the help of the targeted respondents and it was found to be appropriate and it was adopted without any changes made on it.

Data Sample/ Study Period

The data sample represents a judgmental sample of respondents' awareness and supportiveness of the loan scheme to address the inability of students seeking higher education. The sampling covers the various higher institutions within the state and extended to those outside the state.

The study adopted Raosoft calculator to determine the size of the sample from the population of study. A sample size of 377 respondents was arrived at using the calculator and the questionnaires were distributed amongst students of Bayelsa state origin in the various higher institutions of learning. One hundred questionnaires were retrieved from the distributed questionnaires. This shortfall in the total number of retrieved questionnaires was as a result of the lockdown period due to the Covid-19 pandemic. From the data, the researchers will know the aptness of current funding model of higher education that should be applied in Bayelsa State. The study period considered for this research is 2019 and the first quarter of 2020. The Bayelsa State Higher Education Students Loan Board was established as a result of the state governments' declaration of state of emergency on education. The scheme is to make sure that Bayelsa youths have quality education without facing any financial challenges while in school.

Data analysis

The collected data were analyzed using Excel and Microsoft Word as these applications have features for analyzing the collected data with both graphs and charts for the illustration purpose and understanding of the end users of the report. Depending on the questions asked and answers obtained, the researchers underwent the processes of editing the raw data to remove errors and ambiguities. Tables were also used in the analysis for good understanding of the research report. The data collected from the survey using questionnaires were analyzed with SPSS to find frequencies. This helped in explaining the findings logically.

Validity and reliability of research results

The study questions were fully answered since the survey method, which employed use of questionnaire, used to collect data was reliable. Triangulation is also a vital test on reliability of study findings (Mathison, 1988) as different methods are used in collecting data and analyzing them. The findings from this study can be generalized to different wider groups and the trustworthiness of the source of information increases the validity of the study results.

The questionnaire were carefully designed by the researchers to ensure research was perfectly carried out. The study gaps identified in the literature that molded the research questions for this study have to be narrowed since the findings from this study came up with some answers and recommendations.

Patton (2002) argues that reliability and validity of a study are paramount as the audience needs to be convinced of the research findings and the argument here is that the researcher has to trust his sources of information for the qualitative study. The source of information for this study is trusted and hence the results are reliable.

4. Results and Discussion

Data Presentation

The structured research questionnaire used for data collection for this study was administered to three hundred and seventy-seven (377) respondents made up of students of Bayelsa State origin in higher institutions. The institutions include the state own pioneer Niger Delta University (NDU), Federal University Otueke (FUO), University of Africa, Toru-orua (UAT), Bayelsa Medical University (BMU), College of Education (COES), Sagbama and others. Out of the three hundred and seventy-seven (377) questionnaires issued, only one hundred were returned while three hundred and sixty-six were not returned. The low turn up was largely due to the lockdown in the state arising from the Coronavirus pandemic ravaging the entire world. Irrespective of this, the reliability of the responses got from the one hundred respondents from the various institutions remained undisputable. The outcome of the administered questionnaire and responses are showed on table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Administration of Questionnaire and Response Rate

Institution	Questionnaire Distributed	Questionnaire Returned	Questionnaire Not Returned	Response Rate
NDU	160	85	75	22.55%
FUO	60	7	53	1.86%
UAT	51	2	49	0.53%
BMU	35	0	35	0%
COE	35	0	35	0%
OTHERS	36	6	30	1.59%
Total	377	100	277	26.53%

Source: Authors' computation from field survey May, 2020.

Figure 4.1: Multiple Bar Chart of Responses from Bayelsa State students in Higher Education

Source: Authors computation using table 4.1

Figure 4.1 reflects the data in table 4.1 using multiple bar chart for total questionnaire distributed, returned, not returned and the response rate.

Undergraduate Category and Response Rate

Out of the one hundred (100) students that we retrieved their responses, a total of eighty-six (86) were undergraduate students. Of this number, four (4) were in 100 level, 17 in 200 level, 27 in 300 level, 32 in 400 level and 6 in 500 level. No ordinary diploma (OND) and higher diploma (HND) students responded to our questionnaire. Table 4.2 shows the distribution of undergraduate students' level of study and their respective response rate.

Table 4.2: Undergraduate Category and Response Rate

Undergraduate Study Level	Responses	Response Rate
100	4	4.64%
200	17	19.77%
300	27	31.40%
400	32	37.21%
500	6	6.98%
OND	0	0%
HND	0	0%
Total	86	100%

Source: Authors' computation from Field Survey May, 2020.

Table 4.2 further revealed that only 4.64 percent of 100 level student responded, 19.77 percent of the 86 students were in 200 level, 31 percent in 300 level, four hundred level students had the peak of 37.21 percent and 6.98 percent in 500 level were the second least next to 100 level students. This distribution is further given a pictorial presentation using bar chart as seen in figure 4.2 below;

Figure 4.2: Chart of Bayelsa State Undergraduate Students Response Rate

Source: Authors computation using table 4.2

Postgraduate Students Categories and Response Rate

The second segment of the one hundred (100) respondents in this study were postgraduate students of Bayelsa State origin. This group of respondents were fourteen (14) in number and were made up of two (2) Postgraduate Diploma (PGD) students which constituted 14.29 percent in this category, four (4) Master of Science (M.Sc) students which made up 28.57 percent and eight (8) Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) students which constituted 57.14 percent in this category. This is shown on table 4.3 below;

Table 4.3: Categories of Postgraduate Students of Bayelsa State Origin

Postgraduate Category	Reponses	Response Rate
PGD	2	14.29%
M.Sc	4	28.57%
Ph.D	8	57.14%
Total	14	100%

Source: Authors' computation from Field Survey May, 2020.

The distribution of the responses of postgraduate students of Bayelsa State origin from the various institutions of learning are as shown in figure 4.3.

Source: Authors computation using table 4.3

Figure 4.3: Chart of Bayelsa State Postgraduate Students Response Rate

4.2 Socio-Demographic Data

Gender Distribution

The distribution of gender in the current study revealed that of the 100 respondents, forty-nine (49) were males and fifty-one (51) were females across the various higher institutions of learning. Table 4.4 and figure 4.4 below show the gender distribution in this study.

Table 4.4: Gender distribution

Gender	Responses	Response Rate
Male	49	49%
Female	51	51%
Total	100	100%

Source: Authors' computation from Field Survey May, 2020.

Source: Authors computation using table 4.4

Distribution of Sponsorship

A survey of the distribution of funding sources from students in higher institutions of learning of Bayelsa State origin revealed that 63 of the 100 respondents representing 62% are sponsored by parents/guardians, 3 representing

3% are entirely been sponsored by the Bayelsa State Higher Education Student Loan Scheme (BSHESLS), none representing 2% was on scholarship while 32 representing 32% were self-sponsored. Table 4.5 and figure 4.5 show the distribution as seen below;

Table 4.5 Distribution of sponsorship of Bayelsa State students in higher education

Sponsorship	Responses	Response Rate
Parents/Guardian	63	63%
BSHESLS	3	3%
Scholarship	2	2%
Self-Sponsor	32	32%
Total	100	100%

Source: Authors' computation from Field Survey May, 2020.

Source: Authors' computation using table 4.5

Figure 4.5: Chart Showing Distribution of Higher Education Sponsorship

This research makes use of primary data obtained from questionnaires distributed to 377 respondents. However, not all the questionnaires were retrieved as efforts made to retrieve the questionnaires from majority of the respondents was futile due to the Covid-19 pandemic as order to stay at home was strictly obeyed. As a result, one hundred (100) questionnaires were retrieved and were used for the analysis. This chapter, therefore, concerns itself with the analyzing the descriptive data of the respondents, analyzing the inferences of the study, discussion of the results obtained and interpretation of results.

The questionnaire had a question seeking to view from the respondents, on who is responsible for funding their education. The variables of concern were parents/guardian, the BSHESLS, Scholarship and self-sponsored.

Fig 4.1. Bar chart illustration of responses from BSHELS

Source: Authors’ computation

Figure 4.1 shows that a total number of 62 respondents representing 64.58% are been sponsored by their parents or guardians and this implies that attaining a higher academic qualification through tuition fee payment possess a great challenge in the state as majority of the indigenes depends on salary. 33.33% of the respondents are self-sponsored, none of the respondents are beneficiaries of scholarships and only 2.08% representing 2 respondents agreed that they are being sponsored by the BSHELSB.

Research question 1: Have you applied for the Bayelsa State higher education students’ loan scheme?

Table 4.2 Percentage of those applied for loan

Applied for loan	Responses	Percentage
Yes	13	13.40%
No	84	86.60%
Total	97	100%

Source: Authors’ computation from field survey, 2020.

From table 4.2, it is seen that in spite of the high percentage of those with difficulties in paying their tuition fees in table 4.1, only 13 representing 13.40% really applied for the state loan scheme, 84 representing 86.60% refrained from applying for the loan possibly due to lack of adequate information. Figure 4.2 illustrates further the outcome in table 4.2

Figure 4.2 Percentage of students of Bayelsa State origin with tuition fees difficulties

Source: Authors’ derivation using table 4.2

Research question 2: Did you face difficulties in accessing the Bayelsa State higher education student loan?

Table 4.3 Percentage of those who encountered difficulties in accessing the loan

Difficulties in accessing loans	Responses	Percentage
Yes	52	60.47%
No	34	39.53%
Total	86	100%

Source: Authors' computation from field survey, 2020.

From field survey on the experiences of students in accessing loan from the Bayelsa State higher education scheme revealed that 52 representing 60.47% had difficulties in accessing the loan. This figure reinforces the outcome from question 2 which showed low application for the loan earlier. Thirty-four (34) students representing 39.53% had no difficulties in accessing the loan. This is illustrated in figure 4.3 below.

Figure 4.3 Percentage of students of Bayelsa State origin with tuition fees difficulties

Source: Authors' derivation using table 4.3

Research question 3: How long did it take to get the loan?

Table 4.4 Duration of the loan to students in percentage

Duration of the loan	Responses	Percentage
1 -3 weeks	10	25%
1 month	11	27.50%
2 months	19	47.50%
Total	40	100%

Source: Authors' computation from field survey, 2020.

In every application for loan, it is expected that within a week the applicant should know if the loan will be granted or not. However, following the large number of applicants that the board may need to attend to and the processes involved in authenticating the eligibility of applicants as well as the funds procuring procedures involved, the duration may just vary. From the survey result in table 4.4, it is seen that only 40 students were able to access loan between 1 week and 2 months. Majority of the applicants possibly had to wait for much longer periods not covered by the range of options. This is illustrated further in figure 4.4 below

Figure 4.4 Duration of loan to students in categories and percentages

Source: Authors’ derivation using table 4.4

It is also observed that the longer the duration the more loans were granted to students. Between 1 and 3 weeks 10 students representing 25% were granted loan, for the duration of 1 month it increased just marginally to 11 representing 27.50% and rose to 19 students representing 47.50% as seen in figure 4.4 above.

Research question 4: Did you pay to access the loan?

Table 4.5 Financial cost involved in accessing the loan on beneficiaries in percentage

Financial cost involved	Responses	Percentage
Yes	6	10.17%
No	53	89.83%
Total	59	100%

Source: Authors’ computation from field survey, 2020.

In terms of whether financial costs were involved in procuring the loan, the survey result as shown in table 4.5 revealed that 89.83% of the 59 respondents admitted there were no financial cost and only 10.17% or 6 respondent incurred financial cost in procuring the loan. This is illustrated as seen in figure 4.5 below.

Figure 4.4 Duration of loan to students in categories and percentages

Source: Authors’ derivation using table 4.4

Research question 5: Do you think the student loan can enable you complete your study?

Table 4.6 Percentage of students who completed studies with the assistance of the loan

Completion of studies through loan	Responses	Percentage
Yes	64	81.01%
No	15	18.99%
Total	79	100%

Source: Authors' computation from field survey, 2020.

Out of a total of 79 students who found this question pertinent turned in their responses and the result revealed that 64 of the students representing 81.01% were confident of having their studies completed with the loan from the scheme and thus affirmed according, 15 students representing 18.99% however had the reversed opinion.

Figure 4. 6 Completion or otherwise of studies through loan scheme.

Source: Authors' derivation using table 4.4

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study was centered on the manpower development of Higher Education Students Loan Scheme in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Questionnaire were distributed to students of Bayelsa State origin in various higher institutions, ranging from the Niger Delta University (NDU), Federal University Otuoke, University of Africa, Toru-Orua, Bayelsa Medical University, College of Education, Sagbama and other Institutions across Nigeria. Three Hundred and Seventy-Seven (377) questionnaires were distributed and one hundred were retrieved, out of which 86 were responses from undergraduates and 14 were from postgraduate students. The distribution of sponsorship across students of Bayelsa State origin reveal that 63% per cent were sponsored by parent/Guardians, 3% per cent were by Bayelsa Higher Education Students Loan Scheme, 2% per cent are on scholarship while 33% per cent are self-sponsored.

From the foregoing, the high parental/guardian and a reasonable number of self-sponsorship coupled with the low tuition payments by students of Bayelsa State origin is an indication that government intervention in the form of higher education students loan is highly needed to keep students in school and eventual graduation, which shall encourage manpower development in the state.

Recommendations

Based on the above results and findings, the study recommends that the Higher Education Students' Loan Boards should expand its scope beyond payment of school fees. This is because there are other education cost components that are more demanding such as textbooks, accommodation, feeding and upkeep. While, the study shall decline

in making a specific item from the list above to be included in the loan scheme, the study recommends that the loan scheme should incorporate other expenses that are tied to academics as the loan scheme would take students out of the streets completely in search of sourcing for fund to meet other school expenses such as the items listed above. Secondly, the study recommended that the Board should relax its policy on provision of guarantors to access loan and concentrate on withholding certificates as collateral. This recommendation is made because majority of the respondents are afraid of their inability to provide guarantors that are willing to guarantee them to access the loan; thereby, moving about with loan forms in search of guarantor until the time frame to access loan for registration would elapse, and that would require them to suspend their studies even with the presence scheme.

References

- A case study of Palwal and Faridabad district of Haryana. *International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 97 – 103.
- Arora, S. & Kaur, J. (2016). Status of higher education and education loan in India with special reference to Punjab. *An International Journal of Education and Applied Social Sciences*. 7(1), 13 – 21.
- Avery, C., and Turner, S. (2012). Student loans: do college students borrow too much – or not enough? *The Journal of Economic Perspectives* 26(1), 165-192.
- Becker, G. S. (1962). Investment in human capital: A theoretical analysis. *The Journal of Political Economy* 70(5), 9-49.
- Canton, E. & Blom, A. (2004). Can student loans improve accessibility to higher education and student performance? An impact study of the case of SOFES, Mexico. World Bank policy research working paper 3425, October 2004.
- Dewan, A., Goel, R. & Malhotra, R. (2013). Student's perception regarding student financing: Kossey, M.M. & Ishengoma, J.M. (2012) Issues and Challenges of Student Financing Systems in Africa: The case of Tanzania. *Journal of Higher Education in Africa*, 10 (2), 67-90.
- Kyaligonza, R. (2017). Gaps in the implementation of Uganda's students' loan scheme. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 9 (1), 53 – 64.
- Li, W. (2013). The economics of student loan borrowing and repayment. *Business Review Q3*, 1-10.
- Mathison S (1988). Why triangulate? *Educ. Res.* 17(2):13-17.
- Myers, S. C., & Majluf, N. S. (1984). Corporate financing and investment decisions when firms have information that investors do not have. *Journal of Financial Economics* 13(2), 187-221.
- Onen, D., Ajuaba, D.B., Oceng, R.O. & Ndaruhutse, G.R. (2015). Managing the student loan schemes in Africa: Lessons for younger loan schemes. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(12), 271 - 284.
- Oosterbeek, H., & van den Broek, A. (2009). An empirical analysis of borrowing behavior of higher education students in the Netherlands. *Economics of Education Review* 28(2), 170-177.
- Oreopoulos, P., & Petronijevic, U. (2013). Making college worth it: A review of the returns to higher education. *The Future of Children* 23(1), 41-65
- Pannervelam, R. (2011). *Research Methodology*. Asoke K. Ghosh, PHL Learning Private Limited. New Delhi.
- Patra, S., Ray, T. & Chaudhuri, A.R. (2017). Impact of Education Loans on Higher Education: The Indian Experience. Indian statistical institute, Preliminary draft.
- Patton MQ (2002). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Perna, W.L. (2007). Understanding high school students' willingness to borrow to pay college prices. *Scholarly Common*, http://repository.upenn.edu/gse_pubs/181
- Sadiq, A. (2015). The effect of the students' loan scheme on access to higher education in Ghana: A case of Kwame Nkrumah University of science and technology, Kumasi. Unpublished MBA thesis.
- Schwartz, S., & Finnie, R. (2002). Student loans in Canada: An analysis of borrowing and repayment. *Economics of Education Review* 21(5), 497- 512.